

Towards Continuous Integration for Combinatorial Testing

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Abstract—Combinatorial testing is a highly efficient black-box approach that permits practitioners to pseudo-exhaustively cover the input space of a system under test. It offers mathematically guaranteed coverage up to a user-defined strength while requiring only a relatively small number of test cases. Despite these advantages, the industrial uptake of this technique has been slow, not least because of the significant amount of investment required to construct and maintain an accurate input parameter model, create reliable oracles and automate testing processes. This work introduces a hierarchy of embeddings of combinatorial testing into continuous integration and deployment pipelines for use in real-world software development workflows. It further describes the practical implementation of a combinatorial security testing pipeline, enabling automated detection of SQL injection vulnerabilities throughout software evolution. Finally, it details lessons learned throughout the design, deployment and utilization of the resulting processes.

Index Terms—combinatorial testing, combinatorial security testing, continuous integration, test automation, security testing

I. INTRODUCTION

Combinatorial testing (CT) combines mathematically guaranteed input space coverage of a system under test (SUT) with efficient execution through the construction of test sets containing a small number of test cases [1]. Industrial use currently remains limited, likely caused in part by a lack of tool assistance and compatibility with existing real-world testing solutions. This is unfortunate, as CT and its vulnerability-focused counterpart combinatorial security testing (CST) [2] lend themselves to automated testing. Additionally, they permit testers to select a degree of coverage based on available time and requirements, enabling multi-tiered testing processes.

The underlying mathematical structure used in CT/CST is a covering array (CA) [3]. In the context of CT, this is an array where each column corresponds to one parameter and each row encodes a test case. A cell in a CA specifies the value of a parameter during the execution of the test case. To construct a CA, an input parameter model (IPM) and a tester-provided

strength are required. The IPM specifies parameters, their values, and constraints on combinations of parameter values that are permitted to appear in a test. The strength assumes a value between 2 and the number of parameters and is commonly referred to as t in the literature. The defining property of a CA is that whenever one selects up to t distinct parameters, each combination of value assignments for this selection of parameters appears in at least one row of the array. This results in a mathematically guaranteed degree of input space coverage. Higher strengths require a nondecreasing number of test cases, but offer increased fault detection capabilities.

Modern software development lifecycles (SDLC) tend to favor small changes tracked using version control systems such as Git [4]. Continuous integration (CI) pipelines react to incoming changes by cloning the repository, building the project and executing integration tests. The resulting artifacts may be automatically deployed to staging or production environments; this is referred to as continuous deployment (CD).

This work investigates CT in the context of CI/CD. In Section II, we review work related to this concept. Section III details how a CT workflow can be integrated in testing pipelines. We implement a CI/CD pipeline for CST targeting a source code repository of a vulnerable web application and automating the execution of SQLInjector+ [5] in Section IV. Lessons learned throughout this process are discussed in Section V, while Section VI summarizes our contributions and provides an outlook towards future work.

II. RELATED WORK

We are unable to identify prior work focused on the integration of CST into real-world automated software testing workflows. However, multiple works provide guidance towards the practical use of CT. Kuhn, Yu and Kacker [1] offer examples for a variety of testing scenarios. They suggest that assertions embedded in the source code can be used to construct lightweight oracles. Hu et al. [6] investigate the performance of CT in industrial testing scenarios and identify pitfalls, some of which are also addressed in this work. Further works by Kuhn et al. [7], [8] and Segall et al. [9] provide valuable guidance on the implementation of CT methods, but do not directly address practical questions of performance and resource requirements.

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Fig. 1. Overview of combinatorial testing process and hierarchy of embeddings in CI/CD pipelines.

Embedding CT/CST artifacts into development processes as part of source code has the potential to alleviate barriers to adoption. While Fögen and Lichter [10] favor the definition of input parameter models and test cases as classes and methods, a recent work [11] enables developers to utilize source code annotations to create an IPM, specify an oracle and automate the process of model derivation as well as test execution.

The choice of CA generator greatly influences the resource consumption throughout the construction of CAs and their quality. In a recent survey, Leithner et al. [12] provide a large-scale evaluation of generators to support selection processes.

III. METHODOLOGY

This Section describes how CT can be integrated into CI/CD environments, the required artifacts and necessary processes. Figure 1 visualizes a typical CT/CST testing workflow. Initially, an IPM must be created and maintained throughout software evolution. Commonly, this step is performed manually based on documentation and source code. The model and a strength are provided to a CA generator, which constructs a CA representing an abstract test set. The test set is then executed against the SUT (potentially undergoing translation to transform abstract test cases to concrete inputs) and its output – or, depending on the requirements of the oracle, additional characteristics such as database requests or filesystem operations – is recorded. An oracle then outputs a test verdict in the form of a pass or fail decision based on the design specification of the SUT. Optionally, combinatorial fault localization [13] (CT-FLA) may be applied to identify concrete input tuples (i.e. subsets of parameter-value assignments contained in an individual test) that trigger a fault.

Performing these steps as part of a CI/CD pipeline requires additional considerations, as human involvement is reduced to a minimum while the SUT undergoes extensive changes throughout software evolution. Automating steps such as input parameter modeling or the construction of oracles is the subject of active research. Based on these considerations, we describe four variations of CT integration in CI/CD below. They

build upon each other and require iteratively greater investment to set up, but also offer increased flexibility, scalability and performance. For commercial purposes, establishing a pipeline at the *Minimal* or *Standard* level is likely to be the optimal choice at the time of writing, as automated IPM extraction or semi-automated methods using source code annotation as well as fully automated CT-FLA are currently not available at a suitable technology readiness level.

- 1) **Minimal.** This level merely implements test execution (possibly including translation) and an oracle as part of an automated CI/CD pipeline. In the context of CT/CST, this means that a CA based on an up-to-date IPM needs to be precomputed and stored in a manner that is accessible to the pipeline. Changes that modify the external interface of the SUT (e.g. the addition or removal of parameters) require manual maintenance of the IPM. Regardless of whether CT/CST is utilized, capabilities to automatically build the SUT and deploy it to a staging environment must be implemented as part of any CI/CD setup process.
- 2) **Standard.** In this level, covering array generation is performed on demand by the pipeline. This allows for further flexibility: Some testing approaches (including SQLInjector+ [5]) refine IPMs on demand and need to construct CAs on the fly. At the same time, it imposes additional demands on the implementation of the CI/CD pipeline: A CA generator suitable for embedding in an automated workflow must be present and testing jobs may require significantly longer to complete, as CA construction tends to be computationally expensive.
- 3) **Automated IPM Extraction.** Manual creation and maintenance of an IPM is one of the major hurdles to the adoption of CT. Many SUTs lack machine-readable documentation of input parameters; continuous values require extensive effort to model (e.g. using boundary value analysis); and in general, it is infeasible to fully automate the identification of parameter value domains through static analysis due to run-time effects that may

alter the SUT. However, suitable approximations exist: For CST, it is often sufficient to identify endpoints (e.g. individual URLs) that shall be targeted. These approaches are commonly geared towards a class of vulnerability and contain attack grammars to construct IPMs. Development processes that utilize formal specifications may be able to translate such documentation into IPMs, and there exists an approach that uses source code annotations to enable developers to describe an input model alongside the SUT's code [11]. Further improvements in this area would be desirable, e.g. through semi-automated and heuristic methods based on static analysis.

- 4) **Combinatorial Fault Localization.** The purpose of CT-FLA is to pinpoint the inputs that trigger a fault or vulnerability. This reduces the need for manual debugging. Commonly, CT-FLA is either performed as part of an active feedback loop that involves the construction of new test sets [14] or passively using locating arrays [15], which do not require additional CA generation, but generally involve larger initial test sets.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

We implement a continuous integration workflow at the Standard level for CST targeting WAVSEP [16], a Java web application that contains multiple vulnerabilities and aims to provide an evaluation framework for web vulnerability scanners. Using a self-hosted GitLab [4] instance, we create a repository based on WAVSEP 1.5. We automate the build process using Maven [17]. Because testing requires the SUT to be reachable via HTTP, we additionally automate deployment on a Tomcat [18] 8 server. Testing is best performed in an isolated environment, commonly enabled using virtualization techniques such as Docker [19]. Docker Compose was selected as the most suitable choice due to its ability to create containerized environments connected via a virtual network. Figure 2 visualizes the resulting infrastructure: A Maven container used to compile the WAVSEP application, a Tomcat server for hosting the resulting site, and a MySQL container that houses the database underlying the web application.

Fig. 2. Original web application architecture. Java source code is compiled to a web application using Maven, which is subsequently deployed to a Tomcat server and relies on a MySQL database for object persistence. Docker Compose dependencies are visualized using lines ending in a filled circle at the required component, with black dots representing standard dependencies and red dots indicating additional health checks. Dashed lines show data flows.

SQLInjector+ [5] is a combinatorial vulnerability scanner capable of identifying SQL injections, a class of vulnerabilities that may allow an attacker to disclose sensitive information, gain unauthorized access, or perform malicious modifications

to persisted data. It requires a list of endpoints (each of which is defined by a URL, a HTTP parameter, a request method and optionally instructions for authentication). During testing, it utilizes a database proxy that intercepts SQL queries from a web application SUT for the purposes of selecting and fine-tuning an IPM, generates test cases designed to modify the effect of these queries and submits them to the SUT. An oracle evaluates the resulting SQL commands and decides whether a vulnerability has been triggered.

In order to implement a Standard CI/CD pipeline for this target, the following components must be added to the infrastructure shown in Figure 2:

- A list of target URLs
- The database proxy that serves as an oracle; additionally, WAVSEP must be configured to utilize this container as its database.
- SQLInjector+, the output of which must be used by the testing pipeline in order to render a pass/fail decision
- A CA generator; in our implementation, CAGen [20] is packaged in the SQLInjector+ container, allowing it to directly compute CAs (and thus test sets) ad hoc.

Fig. 3. Modified web application architecture resulting from our case study implementing SQLInjector+ vulnerability scanning into a CI/CD pipeline. A database proxy serving as an oracle is inserted between the web application and the underlying database. SQLInjector+ takes the role of a web user.

Figure 3 visualizes the resulting architecture as implemented using Docker Compose. As a final step, the CI/CD functionality of the source code repository management software must be configured to build and test the project whenever new commits are pushed. This is commonly achieved using a configuration file that is committed alongside source code and provides instructions for how building and testing stages are to be performed. Note that our implementation uses Docker-in-Docker. This is required because GitLab CI Runner (the component that retrieves and runs CI/CD jobs for a GitLab instance) is itself distributed as a Docker container by default, but must additionally be able to create and control new containers as defined by our Docker Compose specification.

V. LESSONS LEARNED

The implementation described above was created for the purposes of a training program that aims to equip developers with the skills to perform automated security testing using CST methods. Throughout this process, we were able to gather valuable feedback and insights that we wish to summarize as a list of recommendations below.

- 1) **Cache CAs.** CA construction tends to consume significant time, often in the order of hours or days. While the ability to update IPMs in the face of software evolution is crucial, such changes are infrequent. We recommend to create pipelines that allow for CAs to be cached, even across projects. A recent work on compressed CAs [21] may aid such efforts. If a translation to concrete test cases exists, it may be advisable to also reuse the resulting sets.
- 2) **Take advantage of varying strengths.** Many CI/CD frameworks allow for jobs to be started either through triggers such as new commits or programmatically via APIs. Due to time and resource limitations, it is recommended to perform frequently executed tests with a small combinatorial strength (e.g. $t = 2$) and utilize higher strengths for periodically scheduled large-scale test runs.
- 3) **Streamline IPM maintenance.** The creation and maintenance of suitable IPMs is one of the major factors hindering the practical adoption of CT. Investing in processes and technical capabilities that streamline the translation of existing machine-readable documentation or the extraction of available input parameters is conducive to the successful use of automated CT methods.
- 4) **Keep oracles flexible.** Oracles should be designed with the possibility of changing IPMs (and thus SUT interfaces) in mind and remain capable of returning suitable test verdicts even if parameters are added, removed or altered in terms of their domain.
- 5) **Consider scalability.** In business environments, the expectation is that frequent testing processes (such as those triggered through commits) be completed rapidly, regardless of the number of simultaneous code changes. CI/CD processes must be set up to allow for parallel testing, monitored for performance, and periodically reviewed in order to identify missing or obsolete capabilities.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

CT combines compact test sets with guaranteed mathematical coverage. This makes it an attractive choice for automated testing in SDLCs. However, industrial uptake is limited, not least due to a lack of supporting processes and tooling. In this work, we investigated the embedding of CT into CI/CD environments. We defined a hierarchy of four levels, successively increasing the level of automation at the cost of additional resources during setup. Subsequently, we implement a continuous integration pipeline at the Standard level using GitLab CI that evaluates a web application for SQL injection vulnerabilities using the SQLInjector+ combinatorial security testing prototype upon every change committed to its source

code repository. Lessons learned are summarized with the hope of streamlining the replication by other practitioners.

Our work indicates the need for further research into automated input parameter model extraction and translation from machine-readable documentation; increased automation in other stages of the combinatorial testing process including oracle construction; and solutions that incorporate caching of intermediate artifacts such as test sets to improve scalability.

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